

DAMAGE CHARACTERISATION OF COMPOSITE COMPONENTS USING FULL-FIELD IMAGING TECHNIQUES

Irene Jiménez Fortunato¹, Daniel J. Bull², Janice M. Dulieu-Barton^{3,4} and Ole T. Thomsen^{5,6}

¹ Faculty of Engineering and Physical Sciences, University of Southampton, United Kingdom,
I.Jimenez-Fortunato@soton.ac.uk, www.southampton.ac.uk

² Faculty of Engineering and Physical Sciences, University of Southampton, United Kingdom,
Daniel.Bull@soton.ac.uk, www.southampton.ac.uk

³ Faculty of Engineering and Physical Sciences, University of Southampton, United Kingdom,
janice@soton.ac.uk, www.southampton.ac.uk

⁴ Bristol Composites Institute (ACCIS), University of Bristol, United Kingdom,
janice.barton@bristol.ac.uk, research-information.bristol.ac.uk/

⁵ Faculty of Engineering and Physical Sciences, University of Southampton, United Kingdom,
O.Thomsen@soton.ac.uk, www.southampton.ac.uk

⁶ Bristol Composites Institute (ACCIS), University of Bristol, United Kingdom,
o.thomsen@bristol.ac.uk, research-information.bristol.ac.uk/

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ABSTRACT

Thermoelastic Stress Analysis (TSA) and Digital Image Correlation (DIC) are two well-known full-field imaging techniques that provide surface stress and strains without contacting the test specimen. In the paper, TSA and DIC are carried out simultaneously on a complex composite structure (T-joint) containing different materials (wood, resin, fibre epoxy composite...). The outputs from both techniques are combined to provide a damage parameter that is indicative of the stiffness state of the component. The damage parameter is accurately extracted from the data by placing the images from the two techniques on the same image plane. The data is interpolated so that the images from both techniques are obtained at the same resolution so that they can be combined. It is shown that different materials in the T-joint can be identified and that cracks are also detected. The work demonstrates that TSA and DIC can be applied simultaneously on specimen geometries and loading configurations that are more applicable to the real world.

1 INTRODUCTION

Full-field imaging techniques are non-contact methods that provide data-rich information from the surface of the structure. In particular, TSA [1] and DIC [2] methods have been used to obtain the stress and strain data of metallic [3] and composite [4, 5] components.

TSA is commonly applied with cooled infrared (IR) detectors so-called photon detectors. Photon detectors require a cryogenic cooling system that provides low Noise Equivalent Temperature Difference (NETD) of ~20 mK. However, the need for cooling increases the cost of the IR system significantly, makes the detector heavy and bulky, and limits its life-time. On the other hand, the use of uncooled IR cameras, i.e. microbolometers, for TSA, has been increasing. The main limitations are that the NETD is higher (~40 mK) and more importantly their slow response time means that for specimens subject to cyclic loading (as used in TSA) an attenuation in output signal occurs. Essentially the microbolometer behaves as a low-pass filter, hence the need for calibration to overcome the filtering effect has been established [6-8]. Nevertheless, the cost reduction of one order of magnitude compared with photon detectors, the faster set-up and lighter and more compact nature of bolometers has made them a more attractive proposition for TSA.

Combining IR thermography and DIC has been done in [9] to measure spatial and temporal distributions of temperatures and displacements simultaneously on E-glass/vinyl ester/balsa wood sandwich composite under compressive loading and applied heating in one side. In addition, TSA and DIC techniques have been successfully applied simultaneously in composite coupons [10] during

fatigue test to track damage growth and in metallic components [3] to compensate for the motion in TSA data using DIC displacements, which was demonstrated on a foam cored sandwich structure, and also on metallic welded T-joints [11]. It was Bull et al. [12] who applied TSA and DIC simultaneously to a CFRP spar corner to track damage development of subsurface wrinkles demonstrating the application of TSA and DIC to larger scale composite structure. However, the TSA and DIC data sets were not fully integrated. Hence, the focus of this paper is to combine TSA and DIC at the same image plane to provide a damage parameter. By combining TSA and DIC techniques, the damage level and progression in a structure can be identified. Additionally, it is demonstrated that low-cost microbolometers instead of expensive photon detectors can be used for TSA paving the way for multiple systems to be used on large structures at feasible acquisition costs.

2 EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

TSA [1] relies on the measurement of the temperature of a component whilst it is undergoing a sinusoidal cyclic loading. With a lock-in algorithm [13] the peak-to-peak temperature is obtained and it is related to the sum of the principal stresses [1]:

$$\Delta T = -\frac{T_0}{\rho c_p} (\alpha_1 \Delta \sigma_1 + \alpha_2 \Delta \sigma_2) \quad (1)$$

where ΔT is the temperature change, T_0 is the mean surface temperature, ρ is the density of the material, c_p is specific heat at constant pressure, α is the coefficient of thermal expansion, $\Delta \sigma$ is the stress change and the subscripts 1 and 2 denote the principal material axes.

The authors [8] have determined that when using microbolometers in TSA at different loading frequencies (1 - 11 Hz), it acts as a low-pass filter due to the thermal time constant, which is intrinsic to the sensor material [14]. Therefore, it is necessary to calibrate the measured ΔT at a specific loading frequency to obtain the actual magnitude of ΔT . The calibration approach has been demonstrated in simple coupons, but it requires validation for complex components.

In DIC [2], a speckle pattern applied to the surface of a component is tracked as it undergoes deformation. For sinusoidal loading conditions, it is possible to apply a similar processing procedure to TSA to obtain the peak-to-peak strains using a lock-in algorithm [13]; the process is called lock-in DIC (LIDIC) [13]. LIDIC has the benefit that it can use high resolution cameras, which tend to have low frame rates, instead of expensive high speed cameras for the application of DIC during cyclic loading. It is important to note that the LIDIC obviates the need to synchronise data captured with the maximum and minimum loads of the cycle. Due to the low frame rate of white light cameras for LIDIC the data is under-sampled and the lock-in is performed at an apparent frequency that is lower than the loading frequency of the test. In the present work, stereo LIDIC is applied, which accounts for out-of-plane displacements in the structural component. It should be noted that the lock-in procedure provides magnitude and phase data, and is usable to distinguish between compressive and tensile stresses and strains.

3 INTEGRATION DEMONSTRATION

The demonstrator is a T-joint substructure from a wind turbine blade spar. It is formed by different materials, i.e. wood, resin and glass fibre epoxy composites. The overall dimensions are 400 mm wide, 300 mm height and 50 mm thick. The joint was loaded at 5 ± 4 kN in a specially designed rig in both tension and compression and at different loading frequencies between 1 and 5 Hz.

To perform TSA and LIDIC simultaneously, the surface was first painted with a high emissivity matt black paint to provide a uniform surface emissivity for TSA. Then, white speckles were applied for LIDIC to dehomogenise the surface. Aluminium circular markers, which present good contrast in the microbolometer and white light cameras, were positioned on the specimen to enable the alignment of the TSA and LIDIC data sets onto the same image plane.

The white light cameras have much higher resolution than the microbolometer (10.1 pix/mm vs 2.54 pix/mm). However, DIC and LIDIC relies on tracking subsets of pixels, therefore, the actual resolution of the LIDIC is reduced considerable. In this case, a subset size of 33 pixels and step size of 11 pixels were selected, which gives a spatial resolution of 0.92 subsets/mm. It is necessary to perform

an interpolation procedure to make the resolution of the two image data sets the same. The first step is to align the images by using the markers and then a bicubic interpolation is applied to reduce the resolution of the TSA data to that of the LIDIC. This procedure allows the images to be combined in the non-dimensional form:

$$\frac{\frac{\Delta T}{T_0}}{\Delta \epsilon_{xx} + \Delta \epsilon_{yy}} \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta \epsilon$ is the strain change and the subscripts xx and yy denote the global coordinate axis.

The strains $\Delta \epsilon_{xx}$ and $\Delta \epsilon_{yy}$, are π rad out-of-phase in the recorded LIDIC data (Figure 1). While an element is compressed in x -direction it is tensioned in y -direction, and vice-versa. In the flange of the T-joint it is clear that at the neutral axis strain is zero in the x -direction strain data ($\Delta \epsilon_{xx}$); the phase either side of the neutral axis is π rad different. By knowing the loading direction the strains can be rectified into positive and negative and the data added together and combined with the TSA as shown in equation (2). A combined image is shown in Figure 2(a) showing the distribution of the parameter given by equation (2). As $\Delta T/T_0$ is related to the sum of the principal stresses, the map given in Figure 2(a) is an indication of the stiffness. Areas that have the same stiffness will show as uniform field, hence it is possible to identify the different component materials of the joint. As damage progresses in a fatigue test the stiffness will reduce and this would be apparent in the images. As an example, the scale of Figure 2(a) is reduced in Figure 2(b) to show the presence of a crack between the web and the central core of the T-joint. It should be noted that in Figure 2(a) there are errors in the data around the neutral axis of the flange in the T-joint as well as apparent errors at the edges because of motion present in TSA data.

Figure 1: LIDIC strains and phases for the T-joint loaded in tension

Figure 2: Combined TSA and LIDIC image showing a parameter indicative of the stiffness state, (a) bigger scale than (b)

4 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

It is shown that LIDIC and TSA can be successfully applied simultaneously to a substructure manufactured from different materials. Initial work on the integration of the data has demonstrated the potential of assessing the state of the stiffness of the component and in particular the stiffness of different material regions and orientations. In the future, techniques to eliminate the effect of rigid body motion will be developed. The parameter extracted from both imaging techniques will be studied in depth on composite coupons of different lay-ups subjected to various stress levels to understand the coupling between strain and ΔT . Initial work has been done on $[\pm 45]_{3s}$ GFRP coupons loaded in tension using TSA and LIDIC simultaneously. Figure 3 shows a reduction in ΔT with increasing levels of damage, indicating that the thermoelastic constant has changed with damage, as the tests were done in load control. Further work is required to understand if the thermoelastic response is due to the surface ply only or surface and subsurface plies. It will be studied by comparing the ΔT obtained with TSA and ΔT calculated with LIDIC strains. Additionally, scanning of the samples after testing at different stress levels will help understand the nature of the damage.

Figure 3: ΔT fields after different stress levels (a) 50 MPa and, (b) 202 MPa

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